

Insects for the Green Economy Conference

Theme: Sustainable Food Systems and Livelihoods in Africa

28th – 29th February 2024

CONFERENCE REPORT

G. Sahana, S. Y. Chia, D. Beesigamukama, J. Ng'ang'a, C. M. Tanga, J. Kinyua, M. Ayieko, D. Nakimbugwe, R. Bett, M. Menaga, S. Konyole, J. Anankware, P. Nyeko, S. Niassy, J. Kinyuru, G. Gebreyesus and N. Roos (2024).

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[Link to Book of Abstracts](#)

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Insects for the Green Economy Conference

28-29 February 2024

The Insects for the Green Economy conference ([IGEC](#)) was held on 28–29 February 2024 at the African Institute for Capacity Development ([AICAD](#)) at Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology ([JKUAT](#)), Nairobi, Kenya. The theme of the conference was sustainable food systems and livelihoods in Africa, aiming to explore into the multifaceted roles of insects in driving food security, economic growth, environmental sustainability, and innovation in context of African continent. The organizers were two [DANIDA](#) funded projects, [HEALTHYNSECT](#) and [FLYGENE](#) in collaboration with International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology ([icipe](#)). From understanding the biology and ecology of relevant species to exploring production systems, applications in food and non-food sectors, and the social and economic contexts surrounding insect utilization, this conference provided a comprehensive overview of the potential of insects in enhancing food and nutrition security, promoting environmental sustainability, and driving economic growth.

Amidst the challenges of climate change, population growth, conflicts, and economic instability, it is crucial to explore innovative, nature-based solutions to address food insecurity. Insects, long overlooked as a valuable resource, are now emerging as a novel ‘livestock’ in the food systems. With over 500 species contributing significantly to food and nutrition security in Africa, the potential for leveraging insects in food security is immense. The IGEC explored how insects can transform our food and feed systems, emphasizing both the opportunities and challenges unique to Africa but also in relation to global prospects.

The conference was a landmark event that brought together researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders both African and international, to explore the potential of insects in shaping a sustainable future. Conference participants included experienced and early-stage researchers, students, policymakers, entrepreneurs, and various stakeholders. Through keynote and research project presentations, in-depth discussions, and stakeholder interactions, the participants explored the latest research and innovations driving the insect sector forward both at the local and global levels.

A significant portion of the conference focused on the flourishing field of insect farming and its implications for sustainable protein production, among other uses. Presentations and discussions explored various aspects, including the scalability of insect farming operations, nutritional benefits of insect-based diets, and the regulatory landscape governing insect-derived products. Insights from pioneering research initiatives and successful case studies provided valuable perspectives on overcoming challenges and harnessing the full potential of insect farming to address global food security concerns.

Another prominent theme centered on the role of insects in waste management and the circular economy. Participants delved into innovative approaches leveraging insects to convert organic waste into valuable resources such as biofuels, fertilizers, and animal feed. Case studies highlighting successful waste-to-resource initiatives underscored the transformative potential of insect-driven circular economy solutions in mitigating environmental pollution and promoting resource efficiency. These presentations collectively highlighted the potential of insects in various sectors, including food production, agriculture, and soil enhancement, contributing to

sustainable food systems and livelihoods in Africa. They addressed issues ranging from nutritional value and safety concerns to economic viability and environmental sustainability. Discussions also revolved around the critical importance of insects in biodiversity conservation and the provision of ecosystem services, underscoring the urgent need for conservation efforts and sustainable management practices to safeguard insect diversity and ecosystem resilience.

The conference highlighted the pivotal role of technological innovations in unlocking the full potential of insects for the green economy. Presentations on emerging technologies such as automated insect rearing systems, product processing and insect-based non-food products offered glimpses into the future of insect-related industries. Additionally, discussions on collaborative research initiatives and public-private partnerships underscored the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration in driving innovation and accelerating the adoption of insect-based solutions.

The IGEC served as a catalyst for advancing dialogue, collaboration, and action towards harnessing the transformative potential of insects in building a sustainable future. Through vibrant discussions, insightful presentations, and networking opportunities, participants gained a deeper understanding of the multifaceted roles of insects in driving environmental sustainability, food security, and economic prosperity. The momentum generated by the conference is poised to propel forward the integration of insects into the fabric of food security and green economy.

Summary of participants

Total abstracts = 60

Oral presentations = 26

Posters = 16

Number of participants = 152

Exhibitions = 8

Participating organizations = 55

Inaugural session

The conference was inaugurated by Mr. **Arnold Kipchumba**, Deputy Director - Office of the First Lady of the Republic of Kenya, on behalf of the First Lady of Kenya. He underscored the role of insects in advancing Kenya's vision on food security, environmental sustainability, economic prosperity, green economy and climate resilience, and realization of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals. He underscored the commitment of the First Lady in promoting the integration of insects into food systems and business ventures, to spur economic growth and social progress, in collaboration with various stakeholders. He concluded by calling upon the private sector in Kenya and across Africa to join hands in building the necessary infrastructure and capabilities to support a sustainable and efficient green economy using edible insects.

Nanna Roos presented the conference theme, background, and overarching significance. She outlined the main objectives of the conference, which were to: i) review the state of insect usage for food, feed, and other sectors in Africa; ii) present new research for future development; and iii) facilitate networking and stakeholder interactions. The conference builds on previous initiatives like the 2016 Kisumu conference on insect usage for food and feed. Nanna expressed gratitude to the sponsors, including the Danish Ministry of Foreign Affairs, and acknowledged the efforts of both local and international steering committee members. She introduced the conference topics and keynote presentations, ending her speech by encouraging attendees to enjoy the conference.

Keynote Presentations

The conference commenced with stimulating keynote addresses by expert researchers and policy makers, who underscored the pivotal role of insects in fostering a green economy and highlighted the challenges. The keynotes set the stage for dynamic discussions throughout the two-day conference. The keynote session provided a panoramic view of the current landscape and future prospects of insect farming and consumption, particularly focusing on Africa and beyond. Together, these keynote lectures underscored the significant role of insect farming and consumption in addressing food security, health, and sustainability challenges across diverse contexts. The key points presented are briefly mentioned below.

Dorte Verner, from the World Bank in her keynote address focused on generating knowledge and learning about insect farming for human food and animal feed in Sub-Saharan Africa to enhance food security. She emphasized developing training approaches, implementing pilots, promoting circular economy concepts, sustaining resilience building for refugees and host communities, and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. There is need to increase local capacity for insect-based protein production and provide environmentally friendly solutions with minimal carbon footprint and no harmful land-use changes or biodiversity loss, ultimately contributing to increased food security and livelihoods in Africa.

Grum Gebreyesus, Aarhus University presented aims, objective and current progress of the FLYgene project. FLYgene aims to enhance the efficiency and sustainability of livestock feed production through selective breeding of the black soldier fly (BSF) in Kenya and Uganda. By prioritizing economically important traits and employing innovative phenotyping techniques, the project seeks to implement genetic improvement programs for the economic important traits in BSF both in smallholder and commercial farm settings.

Highlighting the HEALTHYNSECT, project coordinator **Nanna Roos** explained the aim to investigate pathways to accelerate insect farming and consumption in Africa for improved nutrition, health, and livelihoods. By implementing a multisite randomized controlled trial and introducing small-scale farming systems in selected villages, the project seeks to assess the willingness of farmers to adopt insect farming practices and its impact on nutrition and gut health, particularly in infants.

Yupa Hanboonsong, Khon Kaen University, Thailand presented an overview of insect farming and research in Thailand, a country pioneer in commercial insect farming, about rapid development in cricket farming, with the industry matured to include small-scale farms and industrial enterprises. BSF farming, though relatively new in Thailand, shows promising growth with smallholder farmers for livestock feed, and startups emerging for processing BSF products like

pet food and plant fertilizer, indicating a potential for added value products and environmental benefits.

The global atlas of edible insects, compiled and presented by **Saliou Niassy** from AU-IAPSC, revealed over 2,200 insect species consumed across 128 countries worldwide, with Asia leading in diversity followed by North America and Africa. Their study highlights correlations between insect consumption, cultural practices, land cover, population size, and income levels, emphasizing the potential of edible insects to contribute to sustainable food systems globally and the need for proactive efforts to promote their utilization.

The parallel sessions were organized under four broad themes.

1. Insect Species – Biology and Ecology

The session on "Insect Species - Biology and Ecology" provided a comprehensive examination of the biological and ecological aspects of various insect species, shedding light on their genetic diversity, behavior, and interactions within their ecosystems. Presentations delved into the genetic diversity and population structure in BSF, highlighting the importance of understanding local variations for effective management and utilization. Additionally, studies explored selective breeding techniques using a house fly model system, aiming to enhance the commercial traits of insects for various applications. Investigations into the behavior of BSF in artificial mating chambers offered insights into potential optimizations for rearing practices. Furthermore, the session included a morphological description of *Dirhinus* sp., a parasitoid of BSF pupae. Lastly, the impact of communication towers on the performance and behavior of *Apis mellifera* underscored the broader ecological implications of human infrastructure on insect populations. These findings collectively deepen our understanding of insect biology and ecology, crucial for effective management and conservation efforts.

2. Insect production systems

The session on "Insect Production Systems" provided valuable insights into various aspects of insect rearing and management, crucial for sustainable food systems and livelihoods. Presentations covered a range of topics, including the identification and management of insect pathogens and unwanted organisms in production settings, such as the first-hand experiences of smallholder farmers in Uganda rearing edible grasshoppers. Studies also examined the effects of dietary supplementation on the growth and reproductive parameters of edible grasshoppers, as well as the influence of compound diets on the growth and nutrient composition of yellow mealworms. Additionally, innovative approaches like computer-vision-based prediction of body traits and larval sex in black soldier flies were discussed, alongside initiatives in selective breeding and the application of emerging technologies for insect monitoring and rearing. These findings contribute significantly to understanding and optimizing insect production systems for enhanced productivity and sustainability in Africa.

3. Food and non-food application of insects

The session showcased a diverse array of presentations on the multifaceted applications of insects, particularly in food and agriculture sectors, emphasizing sustainable practices and livelihood improvement in Africa. From examining the nutritional quality and safety of edible insect species to exploring the economic benefits of incorporating insect-derived products in animal feed, the presentations underscored the potential of insects as a valuable resource. Additionally, studies delved into consumer perceptions, allergic reactions, and the acceptability

of insect-enriched food products, while also addressing concerns such as heavy metal contamination and microbial safety. Furthermore, innovations like using insect frass as fertilizer for soil enhancement and investigating the antioxidant and antibacterial properties of chitin metabolites demonstrated the broader environmental and health benefits of insect-based solutions. Overall, these presentations collectively highlighted the significant role insects can play in fostering sustainable food systems, improving agricultural productivity, and enhancing livelihoods.

4. Insect in social and economic context

The session on "Insects in Social and Economic Contexts" provided a comprehensive exploration of the potential and challenges surrounding the integration of insects into various social and economic domains. Presentations covered a wide spectrum, from proposing futuristic terminologies like 'Entoculture' and 'entomeat' to describe insect farming and harvested insect flesh, respectively, to practical initiatives like the ReflPro project in Uganda aimed at improving the health, incomes, and nutrition of refugee communities through insect rearing. Studies delved into the cognitive and experiential factors influencing the adoption of insect farming among African farmers, while also examining the implications of scaling insect farming for circular economy and green growth. Eco-innovative technologies and pilot interventions, such as producing yellow mealworms to enhance the nutrition of school children in refugee settlements, were also highlighted. Moreover, research on the challenges and opportunities for edible insects in Tanzania and Uganda provided valuable insights into the current landscape and future prospects for utilizing insects as a sustainable resource in Africa.

Panel discussion

The panelists were:

1. Mr. Alex Mwangi, Site Manager, Chanzi Ltd, Kenya
2. Ms Talash Huijbers, CEO, InsectiPro Ltd, Kenya
3. Mr. Mugagga Kayondo, Agricultural Project Manager, MAMIDECOT Ltd, Uganda
4. Ms Rose Ann, Representative, Black Soldier Fly Association, Kenya
5. Prof. Monica Ayieko, JOOUST, Kenya
6. Ms Line Astrom, Senior Livelihoods and Economic Inclusion Officer, UNHCR

The panel discussion, moderated by Dorte Verner of the World Bank, provided a comprehensive exploration of the opportunities and challenges facing the private sector in scaling up insect production to meet the increasing demand for insect products. Throughout the discussion, panelists shared insights, experiences, and strategies aimed at bridging the gap between the supply and demand for insect-based products. Panelists stressed the importance of collaborative efforts between governments, private sector stakeholders, and research institutions to overcome these hurdles and create an enabling environment for the growth of the insect industry. Furthermore, the discussion highlighted the need for innovative business models, investment in research and development, and the establishment of quality standards to ensure the safety and quality of insect-based products.

Student awards

Oral presentation

Winner: Amos Acur, Makerere University, Effect of supplementing agricultural by-products diets on growth and reproduction parameters of the edible grasshoppers, *Ruspolia differens*.

First runner up Marliyn Muthee: International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology, Effect of preparation methods on nutritional and microbiological safety in edible beetles grubs.

Second runner up: Sarah Nowoya, Aarhus University, Computer-vision based prediction of body traits and larval sex in black soldier fly.

Poster presentation

Winner: Samuel Kiiru, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, Technological impact of *Gryllus bimaculatus* powder in gluten free flours.

First runner up: Mark Ojungu, Makerere University, Production characteristics and constraints of black soldier fly farmers in Uganda.

Second runner up: Nicky Odhiambo, Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology, Effect of cricket enriched complementary porridge and nutrition education on infants and children growth in Siaya County.

Excursions

The conference participants were given an opportunity to explore insect research facilities and ongoing activities at Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology (JKUAT) and the International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology (*icipe*). They were guided through research and demonstration sites dedicated to crickets, mealworms, and black soldier flies within these institutions. The guided tours provided participants with firsthand observations of rearing methodologies, housing infrastructures, feeding protocols, and insights into the major challenges faced and prospects, as elucidated by facility representatives. Furthermore, this experience facilitated valuable networking opportunities among the participants.

Recommendations

From the wealth of engaging presentations, insightful panel discussion, and informative exhibitions over the course of two days, the conference on insect production for green transition in Africa generated consensus recommendations to propel the development and adoption of insect farming as a sustainable solution.

Academia

By focusing on these areas of research and development, academia can play a pivotal role in advancing insect farming practices, thereby contributing to a more sustainable and resilient food system.

1. Continued and enhanced technical research investments:

- a) Allocate resources towards further research in insect production methods, focusing on enhancing efficiency, scalability, and sustainability.
- b) Develop cost-effective and accessible technologies for mass-producing insects for food and feed to make them more economically viable for widespread adoption.
- c) Explore and identify additional insect species suitable for farming to broaden the diversity within the sector and optimize production systems.

2. Identification of economically important traits to target for selective breeding:

- a) Prioritize research efforts towards identifying and understanding economically significant traits in edible insects relevant to African production systems for implementing selective breeding.
- b) Determine traits that enhance market value, nutritional content, and overall profitability of insect farming operations.

3. Consumer awareness and market Development:

- a) Investigate the health and nutritional impacts associated with insect consumption across diverse age groups to promote wider acceptance.
- b) Develop strategies to encourage the adoption of insect farming practices, including effective marketing models that emphasize the benefits of insect-based products.
- c) Document indigenous knowledge related to insect farming for various purposes including food, feed, fertilizer, and therapeutic applications to preserve traditional practices and enhance modern methodologies.

4. Disease management and food safety:

- a) Conduct research to understand disease management strategies in mass production colonies to mitigate risks and ensure the health of farmed insects.
- b) Address food and feed safety concerns throughout the entire production process, including processing, storage, and packaging, to guarantee the quality and safety of insect-derived products.

5. Circular food systems analysis:

- a) Conduct comprehensive analyses of the value chains associated with both farmed and wild insects to optimize resource utilization and minimize waste.
- b) Assess the contributions of insects to sustainable food systems, including their role in waste management, nutrient recycling, and ecosystem services, to maximize their potential within circular economy frameworks.

6. Capacity building and outreach:

- a) Enhance research capacity through investments in infrastructure and training programs to develop physical and human resources for insect production and value chains across Africa.
- b) Develop comprehensive curricula in higher education that integrate the study of insects for various purposes, including food, feed, fertilizer, and waste management.
- c) Promote collaborative, multi-sectoral, and interdisciplinary research initiatives.

- d) Provide support for research capacity building initiatives, including scholarships, fellowships, and exchange programs.
- e) Promote research collaboration between Africa and global partners.
- f) Disseminate knowledge to national, regional and international stakeholders to support the harmonization of standards and policies to achieve Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Government

By implementing these recommendations, governments can create an enabling environment for the sustainable development of insect farming and utilization, contributing to food security, rural development, and environmental sustainability goals.

1. Recognition of insect potential in national strategies:

- a) Governments should formally recognize the multifaceted potential of insects as sources of feed, food, and fertilizer within national strategies and rural development programs. This recognition should encompass the economic, nutritional, and environmental benefits associated with insect farming.
- b) Allocate resources and establish incentives to support the development and expansion of insect farming initiatives, particularly in rural areas where these activities can contribute to poverty reduction and livelihood enhancement.

2. Promotion of policy debates and information exchange:

- a) Governments should actively promote discussions and information exchange on the potential of insects as food and feed among policymakers, stakeholders, and the public. This includes organizing forums, workshops, and campaigns to raise awareness and foster dialogue on the topic.
- b) Lead efforts to introduce insect farming and utilization into policy debates at national and regional levels, ensuring that relevant stakeholders are engaged in the decision-making process.

3. Incorporation of wild insect management in conservation policies:

- a) Governments should incorporate the management and protection of wild edible insects, including their genetic diversity, into natural resources conservation policies and legislation. This involves recognizing the ecological importance of wild insect populations and implementing measures to safeguard their habitats and populations.
- b) Support research and monitoring initiatives to assess the status of wild edible insect populations and identify strategies for their sustainable management and conservation.

4. Creation of enabling policy and legislative environment:

- a) Governments should create an enabling policy and legislative environment for business development in insect farming and market development. This includes streamlining regulations, licensing procedures, and financial support mechanisms to facilitate investment and entrepreneurship in the sector.
- b) Develop and enforce regulations governing the production, consumption, and other utilization of insects, such as organic waste segregation at source, good production

practice manuals, and consumer safety standards, within national and regional environmental and development agendas.

5. Support for research and knowledge exchange:

- a) Governments should provide support for research and knowledge exchange activities among national, regional, and international partners. This includes funding research initiatives, establishing research networks, and facilitating technology transfer and capacity building in insect farming and utilization.
- b) Ensure that biodiversity and conservation strategies for edible insects are integrated into national policies and legislation to promote their sustainable utilization in different market-driven products. This involves identifying and protecting key insect habitats, promoting sustainable harvesting practices, and implementing measures to prevent overexploitation and biodiversity loss.

Development and Investment Partners

The recommendations for development and investment partners aim to catalyze support for insect farming initiatives and promote collaboration in advancing sustainable practices across the value chain.

1. Support stakeholder engagement and harmonized standards:

- a) Development and investment partners should actively support stakeholders' engagement at all levels to develop harmonized standards, legislation, and regulations for the safe production, trade, and utilization of insects as food, feed, and fertilizer.
- b) Facilitate dialogue and collaboration among governments, industry players, research institutions, and civil society organizations to ensure that regulatory frameworks are conducive to the growth of the insect farming sector while prioritizing safety and sustainability.

2. Increase funding opportunities and encourage partnerships:

- a) Increase funding opportunities and encourage partnerships between Africa and global partners to support research, development, and implementation of insect farming initiatives.
- b) Provide financial support for innovative projects and initiatives focused on insects as food, feed, fertilizer, and other related products, fostering collaboration between academia, industry, and governmental organizations.

3. Facilitate knowledge exchange and research expansion:

- a) Facilitate the exchange of knowledge, best practices, and research findings to promote the expansion of research and innovation activities along the insect farming value chain.
- b) Ensure that smallholder family businesses and pro-poor initiatives in vulnerable communities, such as refugee camps, are included in knowledge exchange programs and have access to resources and support to participate in insect farming initiatives.

4. Support private sector partners in insect farming:

- a) Development and investment partners should support private sector partners involved in insect farming by providing financial resources, technical assistance, and capacity building initiatives.
- b) Encourage investment from banks, venture capitalists, sovereign wealth funds, and public institutions in insect farming ventures, particularly those aimed at developing food and feed businesses that prioritize sustainability and social impact.

5. Facilitate global discussions on insect potential:

- a) Foster and support global discussions on the potential of insects as food, feed, and fertilizer to improve global food security and promote more sustainable livestock and crop production systems.
- b) Engage with international organizations, governments, research institutions, and industry stakeholders to raise awareness about the benefits of insect farming and advocate for policy changes that support its integration into mainstream agriculture and food systems.

Private (Industry and Associations) partners

The recommendations for private partners emphasize collaboration, innovation, and market development to unlock the full potential of insects as food, feed, and fertilizer. Here's an elaboration on these points:

1. Facilitating cross exchange of ideas:

- a) Private partners should actively facilitate the exchange of ideas and knowledge between companies, academia, policymakers, government authorities, small-scale farmers, and other stakeholders. This collaboration is essential for developing voluntary best practices that ensure the safe and sustainable production and utilization of insect-based products.
- b) Encourage dialogue and partnership-building initiatives to address challenges and opportunities across the insect value chain, from production to consumption, ensuring alignment with regulatory frameworks and market demands.

2. Improving production technologies and automation:

- a) Private partners should invest in research and development to improve production technologies and automation processes in insect farming. This includes developing innovative solutions to reduce labor requirements, increase profitability, and scale up the volume of insect products for food, feed, and fertilizer applications.
- b) Embrace technological advancements such as precision farming, vertical farming, and IoT (Internet of Things) solutions to optimize production efficiency and resource utilization in insect farming operations.

3. Market development and access:

- a) Private partners should focus on developing market access and marketing strategies for various insect-based products to reach end-users effectively. This involves identifying and targeting niche markets, building consumer awareness and acceptance, and establishing distribution channels that ensure product availability and visibility.

- b) Collaborate with retailers, food manufacturers, and food service providers to incorporate insect-based ingredients and products into their offerings, catering to diverse consumer preferences and dietary needs.

4. Strengthening insect farming associations:

- a) Private partners should support and actively participate in the strengthening and expansion of insect farming associations across Africa and globally. These associations play a vital role in advocating for the interests of insect farmers, shaping policies and legislation, and attracting investments into the sector.
- b) By enhancing the visibility and influence of insect farming associations, private partners can contribute to creating an enabling environment for the growth and development of the insect farming industry, driving innovation, and fostering collaboration among stakeholders.

Annex 1

Conference Program

Insects for the Green Economy Conference

Theme: Sustainable Food Systems and Livelihoods in Africa

Date	28th – 29th February 2024
Venue	The African Institute for Capacity Development (AICAD) at Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology (JKUAT), Nairobi, Kenya.

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

TIME	ACTIVITY/TOPIC	SPEAKER	ORGANIZATION
Day 1: Wed 28th Feb 2024 – Room 1 Chair: Prof. Kinyua; Rapporteur: Dr. Menaga			
08:30 - 09:00	Onsite Registration	Dr. Kinyuru	
09:00 - 09:20	Overview of conference theme	Prof. Nanna Roos	University of Copenhagen, Denmark
09:20 – 09:40	Remarks:	Dr. Abdou Tenkouano	DG, <i>icipe</i> , Kenya
09:40 – 10:00	Remarks	Donor Representative	DANIDA, Denmark
10:00 - 10:20	Remarks	Dr. Dorte Verner	WORLD BANK, USA
10:20 - 10:40	Remarks	Prof. Victoria Ngumi	VC, JKUAT, Kenya
10:40 - 11:00	Remarks	Hon. Franklin Mithika Linturi	Cabinet Secretary, Ministry of Agriculture & Livestock, Kenya
11:00 - 11:30	Chief Guest speech	H.E. Rachel Ruto	First Lady, Kenya
11:30 - 11:50	Group Photo, Tea break & Exhibitions		
Keynote lectures - Room 1; Chair: Prof. Ayieko, Rapporteur: Dr. Ssepuuya			
11:50 - 12:10	Keynote lecture 1: Generate knowledge and learning of insect farming for human food and animal feed for increased food security in Sub-Saharan Africa	Dr. Dorte Verner	WORLD BANK, USA
12:10- 12:30	Keynote lecture 2: Prospects of implementing black soldier fly (BSF) selective breeding in Kenya and Uganda: Status from the FlyGene project	Prof. Grum Gebreyesus	Aarhus University, Denmark
12:30 - 12:50	Keynote lecture 3: Investigating pathways to accelerate insect farming and consumption for health and livelihoods in Africa: The HEALTHYINSECT project	Prof. Nanna	University of Copenhagen, Denmark

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TIME	ACTIVITY/TOPIC	SPEAKER	ORGANIZATION
12:50 - 13:10	Questions and Answers		
13:10 - 14:10	Lunch Break, Poster Session, and Exhibitions		
Breakout Sessions			
Session 1: Room 1 - Insect Species – Biology and Ecology; Insect Production Systems; Chair: Dr. Anankware; Rapporteur: Dr. Nyakeri			
14:10 - 14:25	Unraveling Genetic Diversity and Population Structure of Black Soldier Fly (<i>Hermetia illucens</i>) in Kenya and Uganda	Peter Muchina	JKUAT, Kenya
14:25 - 14:40	Insect pathogens and other unwanted organisms in insect production	Jørgen Eilenberg	University of Copenhagen, Denmark
14:40 - 14:55	First account of smallholder farmers' experiences in rearing edible grasshopper, <i>Ruspolia differens</i> (Serville) (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae), in Uganda	Nyeko Philip	Makerere University, Uganda
14:55 - 15:10	Effects of supplementing agricultural by-product diets on growth and reproductive parameters of the edible grasshopper, <i>Ruspolia differens</i> (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae)	Acur Amos	Makerere University, Uganda
15:10 - 15:25	Computer-vision based prediction of body traits and larval sex in Black Soldier Fly	Nawoya Sarah	Aarhus University, Denmark
15:25 - 15:40	Influence of compound diets on the growth, quality and feed conversion rates of the yellow mealworm (<i>Tenebrio molitor</i> Linnaeus)	Ssepuyya Geoffrey	Kyambogo University, Uganda
15:40 - 15:55	<i>Rhynchophorus phoenicis Fabricius</i> (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) production: a comparative study of different farming protocols	Shadrack Debrah	University of Energy & Natural Resources, Ghana
15:55 - 16:10	Enhancing Attraction and Aggregation of Desert Locusts for Efficient Harvesting: Push-Pull Approach	Joseph Odhiambo	JOUST, Kenya
Session 2: Room 2 - Food and non-food applications of insects/Insects in social & economic contexts; Chair: Dr. Konyole; Rapporteur: Dr. Beesigamukama			
14:10 - 14:25	Preserving nutritional integrity and eliminating microbial health risks in edible rhinoceros beetle grubs (<i>Oryctes sp</i>) through appropriate cooking methods.	Marlyn W. Muthee	Icipe, Kenya
14:25 - 14:40	Black soldier fly larvae meal increases profitability in rabbit (<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>) farming.	Mube K. Hervé	University of Dschang, Cameroon
14:40 - 14:55	Exploring consumer acceptability and allergic reactions of cereal-based porridges enriched with edible insects: A multi-country study	Jeremiah Ng'ang'a	JKUAT, Kenya
14:55 - 15:10	Growth performance and food safety concerns associated with edible cricket (<i>Gryllus bimaculatus</i>) raised on diet enriched with heavy metals.	Susan Mwelwa	Copperbelt University, Zambia
15:10 - 15:25	Futuristic nomenclature for edible insect: 'Entoculture' as a practice of farming insects and 'entomeat' as flesh of harvested insect	John Kinyuru	AICAD, Kenya

TIME	ACTIVITY/TOPIC	SPEAKER	ORGANIZATION
15:25 - 15:40	Improving the health, incomes, and nutrition of refugee communities through the rearing of insects. The approach of the ReflPro project in Kyaka II Refugee settlement, Uganda	Violet Gwokyalya	Mothers Against Malnutrition & Hunger, Uganda
15:40 - 15:55	Do cognitive and experiential factors drive the adoption of insect farming among farmers in Africa? Evidence from three countries	Mohammed Hussen Alemu	University of Copenhagen, Denmark
15:55 - 16:10	Antioxidant and antibacterial activity of metabolites of invitro-digestion and fermentation of chitin	Alex Ndiritu	JKUAT, Kenya
16:10 - 17:00	Tea Break, Poster Session, Exhibitions & Social Interactions		
17:00 - 18:00	Cocktail: Coordinator: Prof. Dorothy Nakimbugwe		
END OF DAY 1			
Day 2: Thu 29th Feb 2024 - Room 1 Chair: Prof. Goutam; Rapporteur: Dr. Chia			
09:10 - 09:30	Keynote lecture 1: From Field to Fork: Edible Insect Product Development and Commercialization in Thailand	Prof. Yupa	Khon Kaen University, Thailand
09:30 - 09:50	Keynote lecture 2: The Global Atlas of Edible Insects: Analysis of Diversity and Commonality Contributing to Food Systems and Sustainability	Dr. Niassy	Africa Union - IAPSC
Session 3: Room 1 - Food and non-food applications of insects/Insects in social & economic contexts; Chair: Prof. Grum; Rapporteur: Dr. Ng'ang'a			
09:50 - 10:05	Total zinc absorption from maize-based meals enriched with edible house crickets in Kenyan pre-school children	Tele Boit	Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands
10:05 - 10:20	Characterization of black soldier fly production systems and traits preferences in Kenya	Rawlynce Bett	UoN, Kenya
10:20 - 10:35	Insect frass fertilizer as circular economy solution for profitable insect farming and improved crop productivity	Dennis Beesigamukama	icipe, Kenya
10:35 - 10:50	Scaling insect farming in sub-Saharan Africa: Implication for circular economy and green growth	Zewdu Abro	icipe, Kenya
10:50 - 11:05	Danish initiatives in selective breeding in insects	Hanne M. Nielsen	Aarhus University, Denmark
Session 4: Room 2 - Food and non-food applications of insects/Insects in social & economic contexts; Chair: Prof. Nyeko; Rapporteur: Dr. Alemu			
09:50 - 10:05	Development of Mealworm-Enriched Snacks and Porridge for Feeding Children in Refugee and Host Communities in Western Uganda	Dorothy Nakimbugwe	Makerere University, Uganda
10:05 - 10:20	Fertigro (BSFF fertilizer) combined with good agricultural practices improves farmer yields on selected crops- a case study of Bomet and Meru counties of Kenya	Mutisya Mary M	InsectiPro Company Limited, Kenya
10:20 - 10:35	Unlocking Soil Enhancement Potential: Black Soldier Fly Frass Amendments in Circular Agriculture	Shaphan Chia	icipe, Kenya

TIME	ACTIVITY/TOPIC	SPEAKER	ORGANIZATION
10:35 - 10:50	Cost-effective aquafeed enriched with <i>Hermetia illucens</i> larvae meal improves growth and fillet quality of Sagana strain of African catfish (<i>Clarias gariepinus</i>)	M. Menaga	icipe, Kenya
10:50 - 11:05	Selective breeding in commercial insects with a house fly model system	Laura S. Hansen	Aarhus University, Denmark
11:05 - 11:35	Tea break		
11:35 - 12:35	Panel discussions – Room 1 Business outlook of the edible insect industry Moderator: Dr. Dorte Verner (World Bank), Rapporteur: Dr. Abro , <i>icipe</i> Panelists: Talash Huijbers (InsectiPro) - Kenya Mugagga (Mamidecot) - Uganda (BSF Association) - Kenya Monica Ayieko (JOOUST) - Kenya		
12:35 - 13:15	Poster Session and Exhibitions.		
13:15 - 14:15	Lunch Break		
Final Session: Closure – Room 1 Chair: Dr. Bett; Rapporteur: Dr. Malinga			
14:15 - 14:25	Student awards		
14:25 - 14:40	Conference overview and resolutions	Dr. Chrysantus Tanga	Head of INSEFF, <i>icipe</i> , Kenya
14:40 - 14:45	Remarks	Prof. Stephen Kiama	VC, UoN, Kenya
14:45 - 14:50	Remarks	Hon. Ann Waiguru	Chair, Council of Governors, Kenya
Fri 1st Mar 2024, 08:00 – 13:00: Field Excursion (JKUAT insect facility & ICIPE)			
END OF THE CONFERENCE!			

Annex 2

List of participants

S/N	Name	Institution/Affiliation*	R: Research C: Company G: Government O: Other	Country
1.	Abdou Tenkouano	ICIPE	R	Kenya
2.	Abigael Nuna	University of Nairobi	R	Kenya
3.	Alex Mutisya	ICIPE	R	Kenya
4.	Alex Ndiritu	JKUAT	R	Kenya
5.	Alice Muchiri	Office of the First Lady	G	Kenya
6.	Alycia Hailu	INSECTARY LTD	C	Kenya
7.	Amos Acur	Makerere University	R	Uganda
8.	Anicia Nobukeye	Gudie Leisure Farm	C	Uganda
9.	Anima Sirma	MOALD-PP&FSD	O	Kenya
10.	Annastacia Maweu	University of Nairobi	R	Kenya
11.	Anthony Karomo	National Mirror	O	Kenya
12.	Antony Kiseno	JAM	O	Kenya
13.	Arnold Kipchumba	Office of the First Lady	G	Kenya
14.	Baligea Stephen	Farm Uganda	C	Uganda
15.	Benter Atieno	JAM	O	Kenya
16.	Bernard Mwangi	AICAD	O	Kenya
17.	Brenda Maragwa	ICIPE	R	Kenya
18.	Brian Amoya	Zihanga Ltd	C	Kenya
19.	Catherine Muiyuro	Media	O	Kenya
20.	Catherine Ndagire	Makerere University	R	Uganda
21.	Charles Ngonga	JOOUST	R	Kenya
22.	Charles Odira	ICIPE	R	Kenya
23.	Chesang Swunukuo	University of Nairobi	R	Kenya
24.	Cosmas Mwikinze	Makerere University	R	Uganda
25.	Daida Nyambura	JKUAT	R	Kenya
26.	Daniel Mutyambai	ICIPE	R	Kenya
27.	Dann Okoth	SCIDEV.NET	O	Kenya
28.	David Kupesa	ICIPE	R	Kenya
29.	David Mugunzi	EntoFeeds Ltd	C	Uganda
30.	Dennis Beesigamukama	ICIPE	R	Kenya
31.	Dominic Byamguba	Director - AICAD	O	Kenya
32.	Dorothy Nakimbugwe	Makerere University	R	Uganda
33.	Dorothy Nyangena	DCA	O	Kenya
34.	Dorte Verner	World Bank	O	United States of America
35.	Edward Ssebbombo	Bobo Eco Farm	C	Uganda
36.	Emmaculate Ouko	JKUAT	R	Kenya
37.	Emmanuel Anedo	ICIPE	R	Kenya

S/N	Name	Institution/Affiliation*	R: Research C: Company G: Government O: Other	Country
38.	Ephraim Gathai	JKUAT	R	Kenya
39.	Eric Maina	Safi Organics	C	Kenya
40.	Eunice Mulango	JKUAT	R	Kenya
41.	Evalyne Ndotono	ICIPE	R	Kenya
42.	Evans Nyakeri	JOOUST	R	Kenya
43.	Faith Nyamu	ICIPE	R	Kenya
44.	Faith Sheila	JKUAT	R	Kenya
45.	Faith Wangui	JKUAT	R	Kenya
46.	Francis Njonge	JKUAT	R	Kenya
47.	Frank Chidawangwa	ICIPE	R	Kenya
48.	Frank Ssemakula	Makerere University	R	Uganda
49.	Geoffrey Malinga	Makerere University	R	Uganda
50.	Geoffrey Ssepuuya	Makerere University	R	Uganda
51.	George Kinyanjui	Destiny Africa	O	Uganda
52.	George Muthui	JKUAT	R	Kenya
53.	Gladys Wakonyo	Dudu ProVentures	R	Kenya
54.	Gloria Cherono	Envirofly	C	Kenya
55.	Goutam Sahana	Aarhus University	R	Denmark
56.	Grum Gebreyesus	Aarhus University	R	Denmark
57.	Hanne Marie Nielsen	Aarhus University	R	Denmark
58.	Hellen Shikanda	Nation Media Group	O	Kenya
59.	Hulunim Gatew	Debre Barhan Univeristy	R	Ethiopia
60.	Irene Shikami	SANERGY	C	Kenya
61.	Isaac Osuga	JKUAT	R	Kenya
62.	Jacob Anankware	UENR	R	Ghana
63.	Jacob Machaki	ICIPE	R	Kenya
64.	Jacob Ngetich	Standard Media Group	O	Kenya
65.	James Fthagu	Nation Media Group	O	Kenya
66.	James Kisaalaye	ICIPE	R	Kenya
67.	Janet Kivuva	MOALD-PP&FSD	G	Kenya
68.	Javan Odhiambo	AICAD	O	Kenya
69.	Jayne Mugue	Kenyatta University	R	Kenya
70.	Jeremiah Nganga	JKUAT	R	Kenya
71.	John Kinyuru	AICAD/ JKUAT	R	Kenya
72.	John Njagi	AICAD	O	Kenya
73.	John Odhiambo	JKUAT	R	Kenya
74.	Johnson Kinyua	JKUAT	R	Kenya
75.	Jorgen Eileuberg	University of Copenhagen	R	Denmark
76.	Joseph Odhiabo Aguk	JOOUST	R	Kenya
77.	Joshua Wambua	ICIPE	R	Kenya
78.	Joyce Njenga	JKUAT	R	Kenya

S/N	Name	Institution/Affiliation*	R: Research C: Company G: Government O: Other	Country
79.	Kabuye Benjamin	Makerere University	R	Uganda
80.	Kayizzi Robert	MAMAH	O	Uganda
81.	Kayondo Mugagga	MAMIDECOT	C	Uganda
82.	Kennedy Otieno	JAM	O	Kenya
83.	Kevin Waithaka	JKUAT	R	Kenya
84.	Laura Hansen	Aarhus University	R	Denmark
85.	Laura Stanbrd	Loop Pet Food	C	-
86.	Lawrence Ouma	ICIPE	R	Kenya
87.	Lenjir Jesse	JKUAT	R	Kenya
88.	Line Astrom	UNHCR	O	Switzerland
89.	Linus Wamai	ICIPE	R	Kenya
90.	Liz Nganga	ICIPE	R	Kenya
91.	Mach Paul	ICIPE	R	Kenya
92.	Makumbe Godknows	JacqueAlex	O	-
93.	Manwa Bildad	JKUAT	R	Kenya
94.	Margaret Kababu	ICIPE	R	Kenya
95.	Marian Peter	NGN/ Flyingfood	C	Netherlands
96.	Mark Ojungu	Makerere University	R	Uganda
97.	Marlin Muthee	ICIPE	R	Kenya
98.	Martin Njorogr	FLYBOX	C	Kenya
99.	Mary Mutisya	InsectiPro	C	Kenya
100.	Mathilde Miedewa	TNO	C	Netherlands
101.	Menaga Meenakshisundaram	ICIPE	R	Kenya
102.	Meshack Kimondo	JKUATES	C	Kenya
103.	Minica Ayieko	JOOUST	R	Kenya
104.	Mohammed Alemu	University of Copenhagen	R	Denmark
105.	Monicah Sammy	CORDAID	O	Kenya
106.	Mube Herve	University of Dschang	R	Cameroon
107.	Nancy Ndungu	JKUAT	R	Kenya
108.	Nanna Roos	University of Copenhagen	R	Denmark
109.	Nawoya Sarah	Makerere University	R	Uganda
110.	Nduta Muniu	JKUAT	R	Kenya
111.	Nicholas Ndekei	Zihanga Ltd	C	Kenya
112.	Nicky Okeyo	MMUST	R	Kenya
113.	Noella Kugehi	ICIPE	R	Kenya
114.	Nthuku Mumo	GCX Farm	C	Kenya
115.	Nuria Mohamed Salim	WATOTO GO GREEN	C	Kenya
116.	Okot Ribon Musoga	Makerere University	R	Uganda
117.	Paul Kibogo	ICIPE	R	Kenya
118.	Paul Ndegwa	University of Nairobi	R	Kenya
119.	Peter Kamau	JKUATES	C	Kenya

S/N	Name	Institution/Affiliation*	R: Research C: Company G: Government O: Other	Country
120.	Peter Muchina	JKUAT/ ICIPE	R	Kenya
121.	Peter Musembi	ICIPE	R	Kenya
122.	Peter Tuyisenge	Gudie Leisure Farm	C	Uganda
123.	Philip Nyeko	Makerere University	R	Uganda
124.	Rawlynce Bett	Univeristy of Nairobi	R	Kenya
125.	Robert Nesta	JKUAT	R	Kenya
126.	Roseanne Mwangi	INSECTARY LTD	C	Kenya
127.	Roseline Akol	Makerere University	R	Uganda
128.	Sadhat Wahisimbi	Makerere University	R	Uganda
129.	Saliou Niassy	AU-IAPSC	G	Cameroon
130.	Sam Muniu	JKUAT	R	Kenya
131.	Samuel Imathiu	JKUAT	R	Kenya
132.	Samuel Jerry Odindo	JOOUST	R	Kenya
133.	Samuel Kiiru	JKUAT	R	Kenya
134.	Shadrack Debrah	UENR	R	Ghana
135.	Shadrack Kibet	KCIC	C	Kenya
136.	Shane Jane	JKUAT	R	Kenya
137.	Shaphan Chia	ICIPE	R	Kenya
138.	Silvenus Konyole	MMUST	R	Kenya
139.	Stella Maina	JKUAT	R	Kenya
140.	Sunday Ekesi	ICIPE	R	Kenya
141.	Tanga Mbi	ICIPE	R	Kenya
142.	Tele Boit	University of Copenhagen	R	Denmark
143.	Teresia Karanja	MOALD-PP&FSD	G	Kenya
144.	Thomas Spranghers	VIVES	R	Belgium
145.	V.S. Menon	Kamanu Farm Ltd	C	Kenya
146.	Victor Korir	AICAD	O	Kenya
147.	Victory Wangui	Media	O	Kenya
148.	Violet Gwokyalya	MAMAH	O	Uganda
149.	Winnie Chepkemoi	SANERGY	C	Kenya
150.	Winnie Wambui	Harcourt ECO FARM Ltd	C	Kenya
151.	Yupa Hanboonsong	KKU	R	Thailand
152.	Zewdo Abro	ICIPE	R	Kenya
153.	Zeynab Wandati	Nation Media Group	O	Kenya

*Abbreviated institution

Abbreviations	Full name
AICAD	African Institute for Capacity Building and Development
AU-IAPSC	Inter-African Phytosanitary Council of African Union
CORDAID	Catholic Organization for Relief and Development
DCA	DanChurchAid
EAGC	Eastern Africa Grain Council
ICIPE	International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology
JAM	Justice and Mercy (JAM) Community Int. Project
JKUAT	Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology
JKUATES	Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology- Enterprises Ltd.
JOUST	Jaramogi Oginga Odinga University of Science and Technology
KCIC	Kenya Climate Innovation Center
KKU	Khon Kaen University
MAMAH	Mothers Against Malnutrition and Hunger
MAMIDECOT	Masaka Microfinance and Development Cooperative Trust Ltd
MMUST	Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology
MOALD-PP&FSD	Ministry Of Agriculture, And Livestock Development, Plant Protection and Food Safety Directorate
SCIDEV.NET	Bringing science & development together through news & analysis
TNO	Innovation for life
UENR	University of Energy and Natural Resources
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

Insects for the Green Economy Conference

Theme: Sustainable Food Systems and Livelihoods in Africa

28th – 29th February 2024

